

Kherwar Saints: The Freedom Fighter of Santal Tribes

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Abstract:

This is a very significant fact that the mutiny of 1857 in Jharkhand began in the Rohini village of Santhal Pargana, but this revolt like in other parts of Jharkhand never spread among the civilians and specially among the local tribals in Santal Pargana. It so happened because the British government adopted several reform measures in the administration of the Santal area after the Hul of 1855, which satisfied the Santal people. By the Act 37th of 22nd December 1855 a new territory was formed in and around Damin-i-Koh into a separate non-regulation district, called as Santal Pargana which was divided into four sub-districts- Dumka, Deoghar, Godda, and Rajmahal. They were placed under a Deputy Commissioner and four Assistant Commissioners with civil and criminal jurisdiction over the area.¹ This was followed by the introduction of the Police Rules of 1856 which recognized the tribal headman system (Manjhi, Parganait) and gave Police powers to village officials which is known as Yule's Rule. The government also tried to control interest rates and thus provided safeguards to protect Santals from the clutches of Moneylenders, Zamindars and other outsider exploiters. The essence of the newly introduced system was that the ruler and the ruled should have direct access to each other.² The system worked well under Commissioner Yule and Deputy Commissioner Eden but the situation began to change after their departure. The administrative system relapsed with misgovernance. The moneylenders, outsider exploiters and government Amlahs once again entered into the scene. The discontentment was further fuelled by adversity caused by the poverty, famine and pestilence.

The Santals had taken lessons from the ruthless suppression of Hul (1855-56) and so, they chose not to resort to arms struggle. Rather the Santals had decided to organize a movement to construct a more satisfactory culture to reach their political goal.³ Therefore to meet the challenge Kherwar Saints like Bhagirath Tribhuvan Manjhi and Dubia Gossain took the lead. They advocated religious reforms as a possible escape from the sufferings. Their movement was firstly religious in nature yet it had elements of social, economic, agrarian and political nature as it sought for the establishment of Santal Raj.

In 1874 Bhagirath Manjhi of Tardiha Village in Godda subdivision declared to the Santals that God had sent him to redress their grievances and to found Santal Raj. Which would be free from all kinds of sufferings and exploitations. He became a hermit, his followers called him 'Babaji'. In his discourse he asked his disciple to live a pure life of vegetarianism and non-violence. He also asked his followers to abstain from drinking intoxicants, and other evil practices which entered into traditional religion of Santals. Due to such pious philosophy and pure as well as plain living style they were also called as Sapha-Hor or Pure Man. A Shrine was also built at Tardiha village. Bhagirath Manjhi was declared as the King of Santal's Raj. He started collecting rent from the people, and asked them not to pay rent either to government or the Zamindars. This movement became very popular among the Santals. Several thousand Santals visited his place at Tardiha. His followers were present in whole of Santal Pargana specially at Rajmahal area.

The popularity of the movement soon alerted the British government who arrested Bhagirath Manjhi and imprisoned him for two years. In order to crush the movement his shrine was also demolished by the government. Thus it is clear that colonial government well understood the political motive of the Movement behind the mass mobilization of the Santals by him. After his release from jail Bhagirath Manjhi secretly continued his activities which led to a fresh spurt of movement in the year of 1881 under the leadership of Dubia Gossain.⁴

Dubia Gossain was a Hindu ascetic belonged to Jagesai in Hazaribagh. He experienced that idea of Kherwarism was still continued to be a living influence on Santals. However the immediate cause of movement under Dubia was connected with census of 1881, to which Santals mistook as an official effort to convert them to Christianity, and to recruit them for Afghan wars. Similar to Bhagirath, Dubia also advocated Socio-religious reforms to eradicate all the sufferings of Santals. He asked his followers to abstain from drinking intoxicants, meat eating and all the evil practices like witchcraft and worship of Spirits and others. He also said that Santals under his leadership by adopting pure and plain life of Kherwarism ideology could easily attain their self rule. Thus he held out the hope of establishment of Santal Raj among his followers. Where there would be no sufferings or oppression of Santals either by landlords, moneylenders, Zamindars, or Colonial government. He soon became very popular among the Santals. His message spread like wild fire on whole of Santal Pargana. Santals started looking at him as a Messiah and Liberator.

Dubia after mass mobilization of Santals started implementing his Political goal. He gave slogan to the santals that “we are our own Hakims we will not obey orders of any other Hakim.” Clearly Santals under the leadership of Dubia Gossain tried to establish their own rule. These incidents were clearly posing a threat and challenged the British rule in Santal area. By February 1881, the British government feared a general uprising of the Santals in the area. As a preventive measure large number of troops were deployed in the area. Dubia Gossain was arrested and deported to Lucknow as a political prisoner. Apart from this all close associates and sympathetic Santal leaders were imprisoned. In order to avoid any protest or revolt Armed Police was permanently stationed in Santhal Pargana till 1893.⁵ Thus the punitive actions by the government led to crush Dubia’s movement.

The religious revitalization of Kherwar saints seems to be a means to achieve a political end in the form of establishment of Santal Raj. During the movement the Kherwar saints in a very short period could mobilize support of more than 50,000 Santal followers. Thus we find its religious and political messages reached to a large number of Santal population. Although the political aspect of the movement was suppressed by the British government but its message remained alive among the Santals, when we find that the Sapha Hors campaigned for non payment of rent to the government, during the Non Cooperation Movement (1920-22). Further we find growth of nationalist character among Santhals as they started worshipping Bharat Mata in the decade of 1930s. in anticipation to attain self rule from colonial power. The Kherwar movement was a reformative movement which included elements of agrarian unrest and oppression by colonial government and outsider exploiters. It is said that there was an essential link between adversity and revivalism or Kherwarism, as the dormant memory of God was awakened when extraordinary adverse condition took place in the form of deadly combination of oppressive rule and famine.⁶ The Santals found that their Gods and faith in various spirits was proving helpless in their role of deliverances. Thus they borrowed the faith of Hindus and also associated their lifestyle such as vegetarianism. Warding of evil became important for them, otherwise they believed that God would not bless them. For example Bhagirath Manjhi had declared that- “Our Father we have sinned (100%) when our sins are fully atoned for we shall be the owners of our country.”⁷

The cult had three sub-sects. First was purest or real Sapha-Hors who worshipped Singhbahini or Goddess Durga and Sun God. They absolutely abstained from meat eating drinking intoxicants and dancing. They took daily bath.

Second sect was called Babajias or mendicants whose profession was to traverse the country and to beg. Third sect was called as Bhelwaragars or half hearted Sapha-Hors who joined in all other observance of Kherwarism whilst retaining their old customs.⁸

MacDougall after a detailed study of Kherwarism ideology made a list of chief features⁹ of it as---

----- Kherwar leaders were chosen by the God to show the right path and religion to the

Santals.

----- The Santals should only worship deities prescribed by the Kherwar leaders and they had to observe the rituals laid down by them.

----- Those who disobey the leaders will receive divine punishment.

----- Those who do perform the new rituals will become happy and prosperous.

----- Due to these ideologies of Kherwarism Golden age of Santals will be reestablished. Where there will be no place for government officials, landlords, Christians and any outsider exploiters.

The aim of this religious revitalization movement of the Santals was to strengthen the community morally to end their material sufferings, so that their days of golden past will be restored. There were a general belief among the Santals that all the adversaries experienced by the Santals was due to wrong religious practices. Bhagirath Manjhi also highlighted the issue and said that traditional Santal spirits failed to prevent the famines of 1874 as they became weak, according to him the power could be invoked from the worship of Singbahini the goddess of Zamindars.¹⁰

One significant aspect is that during the Santal Hul (1855-56) the outsider exploiters or Dikus reacted against the rebels actively, as they not only helped British Army by providing information regarding the whereabouts as well as movements of the rebels. The Dikus also used legal means such as lawsuits against the Santals. Thus we find that these outsider exploiters or Dikus fought a proxy war against the Santal rebels as they did whatever they could against the rebels. On the other hand these Dikus were so frightened during the Kherwar Movement that they deserted the area. It proved the popularity of this widespread movement in Santal country. Interestingly Christian missionaries also took a hostile stance against the Kherwar movement and their leaders. They provided the colonial government with information of the activities of the Kherwars and counter attacked their religious propaganda. The missionaries even tried their best to convert some of the Kherwar leaders. Further the missionaries claimed that all the Kherwar leaders had Christian orientation or background in their early career so that teachings of Kherwar leaders had similarities with Christian doctrine.¹¹ Basically

till that time Christian missionaries were spreading its ideologies and converted a large number of tribals in whole of Jharkhand area, thus they were particularly against any religious revitalization movement in any of the traditional tribal religion. The Christian missionaries knew that success of Kherwarism will put an end to all the opportunities of conversion of Santals into the faith so, naturally the missionaries were critical against Kherwarism and its leaders.

Contemporary British sources suggests that Kherwar movement was not a popular movement as its leaders and Santal village headmen had restricted their interaction with a limited number of persons who were close to them .They did not made any contact with the people of other tribe, caste and religion. Therefore it failed to attract the common people and other than Santals residing in the same village . Thus it never took shape of a mass movement. However, this view is true in its religious aspect only. Kherwarism was not only a revitalization movement. The movement also had nature of agrarian and political character which had attracted a large number of people. Apart from Santals other low caste Hindus and Muslims lived there also joined the movement specially on land rent and census issues. The movement however failed to achieve its aim of agrarian reforms or to attain the political goal of Swaraj. There were several causes behind the failures such as the two upsurge under Bhagirath and Dubia were not closely related with each other.¹² Further they did not have enough resources to fight mighty colonial power. Whatever so this religious revitalization movement was basically a means to achieve political end. Its roots were agrarian a simple premise on which the political credo was built.¹³

In short we could say that when Santals were reeling under hopeless and pathetic condition due to exploitative colonial rule, the Kherwar saints rekindled their hope of restoration of their own rule .

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